

Canvas Badges Quick Start Guide

Suggestions and tips for accessing and sharing badges awarded by CSCCE

Created by staff at the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE)

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About the guide

Welcome to Canvas Badges, a global platform that can be used to mint and share digital badges. CSCCE uses Canvas Badges to award digital badges to learners who have successfully completed our trainings. You can read more about the motivation behind this approach [in this blog post](#).

This guide contains some quick tips to help you to configure and use Canvas Badges. They are organized into three key areas that describe:

1. Badge access and account creation
2. Using the Canvas Badges Backpack to store and organize badges
3. Sharing your new badge

Any questions? Email: tech.help@cscce.org

Note: *Canvas Badges was previously called Badgr. The issuing organization for badges should appear as Canvas Credentials or Canvas Badges, but some things, such as URLs, may still say "Badgr."*

Acknowledgements

CSCCE uses the CREDiT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

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Citing and reusing this guide

CITATION AND REUSE

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Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2023) Canvas Badges Quick Start Guide: Suggestions and tips for accessing and sharing badges awarded by CSCCE. Martinic, Pratt, and Woodley doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10287185](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10287185)

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Last updated December 2023

1. Badge access and account creation

Congratulations on earning a digital badge from CSCCE! New graduates can expect to receive an email from Canvas Badges (noreply@badgr.com) with the subject line “Congratulations, you earned a badge!” The email contains the badge image, title of the training, description, and options to download the badge image and create an account with Canvas Badges.

To access your badge, log in or create a Canvas Badges account:

- If you do not already have an account, create a new account using the email address at which you received your badge. You can add additional email addresses in your account settings later.
- If you already have a Badgr or Canvas Badges account linked to a different email address, log in with your existing account details. Then, click the person icon at the top right, select Account settings, and add the email where your CSCCE badge was received. After verification, your CSCCE badge will appear in your Canvas Badges Backpack.

2. Using the Canvas Badges Backpack to store and organize badges

The Canvas Badges Backpack is a badge storage location for all Open Badges. Click a badge to see more details about it including the awardee name and email, issue date and time, description, and earning criteria. Learn more about [Using the Canvas Badges Backpack](#).

- **Badges** – All badges awarded by Canvas Badges and delivered to the email address(es) in your account will automatically appear here. You can choose to upload Open Badges from other platforms and also to group badges by issuer (e.g., CSCCE).
- **Collections** - You can also create a collection to organize your badges. Learn more about [Creating a collection of badges in Canvas Badges](#).

3. Sharing your new badge

Now you've claimed your badge, it's time to share it with your networks! You can share badges in a number of different ways. Click the "Share" button in the top right to display a box with sharing options. **The link in the link tab of this dialog box is your personalized verification URL which verifies that you are the recipient, so it is important to always copy this when sharing via link!** Do not check the option to show email address unless you are sharing your badge somewhere your email address is already available.

Here are some suggestions for where to start sharing:

Sharing your badge on LinkedIn

There are two ways to share your new credential on LinkedIn:

1. Add as a credential so that anyone viewing your profile can see your training
2. Share with your colleagues as a post in your feed

To add the badge to your credentials through the Canvas Badges Backpack, click the “Add to profile” button in the **social tab** of the dialog box. LinkedIn defaults to “Canvas Badges” as the *Issuing organization* but you can edit the certification and search for “Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement” to update this. Then the image next to the text shows CSCCE’s umbel logo instead of the Canvas logo.

To share your badge in your feed, copy and paste your personalized link and then add a note about your experience taking the course.

Sharing your badge on social media

You can also share your personalized link in a post on X, Mastodon, or on any other social media platform and it will show a preview of your badge.

Adding your badge to your email signature

Everyone’s approach to email is a little different, and we know that email clients vary in functionality. However, by means of an example, here’s how you can add your badge to your email signature in Gmail:

- Download the badge as a PNG file to your computer (either from the Canvas Badges email or by clicking the ellipses next to the Share button when viewing your badge on the Canvas Badges website)
- Copy your personalized verification URL
- Go to settings and select “add an image” to your signature, embedding the personalized URL as a hyperlink

The hyperlink verifies your credential, and ensures that anyone clicking it sees that you have indeed earned the badge.

Adding your badge to your website

Canvas Badges also provides you with HTML code as an iframe, which allows you to embed your badge on a website. In the **HTML tab**, select which version of the badge you would like to embed, a

Card or Badge view. Cards show additional context and Badges show the badge image, but both have the badge metadata. Select the Copy button and then paste the code wherever HTML is allowed.

More information about sharing your badge

Find detailed directions for how to share badges in this guide: [Sharing badges from Canvas Badges/Credentials](#), or if you have any questions, email tech.help@cscce.org.

That's it – you're good to go!